

Mind the Gap – Students' Perspective on Relevant Competencies Needed and Gained in Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

There are numerous discourses about competencies of future engineers as well as the challenge to learn, teach and assess them. In particular, this applies for the question of which competencies – besides technical knowledge and understanding – are relevant for future engineers in order to responsibly address the needs of society. This paper contains the initial results of an ongoing research project which aims to investigate engineering students' competencies and their perception thereof. In the context of a recurring engineering master's seminar at RWTH Aachen University the participants conducted interviews with a total of 41 students from outside the course. The interview subjects were themselves master's students from diverse engineering programs. In the interviews, the subjects were asked by their peers, among other things, which competencies they consider relevant for engineers and to what extent they have acquired these in their studies. The answers to those questions are evaluated and discussed in this work. The results show gaps in the acquisition of competencies – from the students' point of view – and in particular a discrepancy

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between the perceived relevance of competencies and the acquisition of these in the study programs. Besides problem solving, and technical knowledge and understanding, students pointed out that social competencies, such as communication and teamwork are particularly relevant. At the same time, they saw a lack of acquisition of these competencies in their study. The same applies for missing integration of knowledge into practical application.

1 INTRODUCTION

Research and practice within engineering education are framed by growing discourses about competencies of future engineers. This goes along with the need for both student-centred learning and integrated curriculum development in order to synthesize students' knowledge and to prepare them as future professionals [1, 2]. Moreover, as future professionals, engineering graduates must acquire a broad range of interpersonal and personal competencies that go beyond siloed technical knowledge [2, 3]. This concerns competencies for sustainable development as well as professional identity with regard to responsibility and influence on society. However, those insights are well established. Already, 20 years ago, for example [1, 4] called for a more student-centred and outcome-oriented engineering education. The same applies for the CDIO initiative, which published its first syllabus in 2001 [5].

Several literature reviews focused on competencies engineering programs should emphasize and engineering students should gain [e.g. 6, 7]. Common findings are the need for personal and interpersonal competencies, especially with regard to communication, teamwork and problem solving. At the same time, surveys with engineering students showed that they do not feel well prepared for career entry, as those competencies are lacking in their study programs [8, 9]. Often, this also goes along with an education focused on putting theoretical knowledge before practical applications [10, 11] or a lack of knowing how to integrate knowledge into application [12]. For example, in the study by Miranda et al. [8] civil engineering students emphasized that they primarily learn technical knowledge and perceive themselves in a passive role, rather than having hands-on experience. Applying and integrating theoretical knowledge to real-world problems influences students' perceptions of their engineering profession, thereby reflecting on the need for interpersonal skills, such as teamwork – which surprised several students in the study by Hughes et al. [13]. The results show that students' perception about their engineering profession is often narrow and based on disciplinary and technical knowledge, which is also in line with the results of other studies [e.g. 11, 14].

Building on that and considering the lack of qualitative research about students' perception of their competencies [15], this study focuses on engineering students' perception with regard to the most relevant competencies needed for professional engineers and their acquisition within their study programs. The study aimed to answer the following research questions:

What competencies for engineers do master's students in engineering consider relevant – and why?

To what extent are these competencies acquired in their studies?

2 METHODOLOGY

In the context of a recurring engineering master's seminar at RWTH Aachen University the participants conducted an interview each with a total of 41 students from outside the course. The aim of the course was to find out, through student-led interviews, which competencies engineering students consider relevant to be able to cope with future challenges. The teaching concept is described in detail in [16] and will therefore not be discussed further. Instead, the following is a partial evaluation of the student-led interviews on relevant competencies of engineers.

The interview subjects were themselves master's students from diverse engineering programs (see Figure 1) and recruited by the students from the course. A majority of the interview subjects studied either civil or mechanical engineering. In the interviews, the subjects were asked by their peers, among other things, which competencies they consider relevant for engineers and to what extent they have acquired these in their studies. Here, the interviewed students answered freely without being given a prior choice of competencies. Note that this is a partial evaluation. In a next step, the competencies mentioned will be analyzed further with regard to the students' perspectives on engineering responsibility and identity. A notable limitation is that the interviews were not conducted by one person, but by 41 individual student interviewers. To address this, an interview guide was developed and provided for by the instructor. All interviews were recorded and the original audio files were used for further analysis.

All 41 student-led interviews were then analyzed qualitatively by the authors in order to answer the predefined research questions. In doing so, the interviews were systematically screened for competencies that students deemed relevant.

Figure 1. Study programs of surveyed master's students

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 provides an overview of both all competencies mentioned by the students as relevant for engineers and all competencies mentioned by the students as perceived as missing in their studies. The number of mentions does not serve as statistical analysis, but is intended to give an idea and to illustrate the respective distribution.

Note that the listed (translated) competencies were mentioned by the students *themselves* [16]. We deliberately did not categorize the competencies in order to transparently present the students' assessment and perception without any biases of the authors. However, there are several frameworks and studies that group teamwork and communication as social competencies, often described as interpersonal skills [e.g. 5, 13]. The fact that students name the respective competencies differently can be attributed to a lack of knowledge about them and the different ways of describing competencies [6, 7, 17].

Problem solving, and technical knowledge and understanding were mentioned most frequently as relevant competencies by students. In general, the students considered these competencies to be central characteristics of engineers, also with regard to their own perceived engineering identity. One student from business administration and civil engineering described that in the following way:

"A person who is very independent. A person who is so self-sufficient that when she/he has a problem, she/he has a good solution and can structurally go to this problem and solve this problem by providing certain tools, mainly related to the technical. The implementation of technical problems – this is for me an engineer."

Note that all quotes were translated from German to English by the authors.

Table 1. Relevant and missing competencies for engineers – students' perspective

Rank	Relevant competencies for engineers (# mentions)	Rank	Competencies missing in studies (# mentions)
1	Problem Solving (33)	1	Social Competence (17)
2	Technical Knowledge and Understanding (27)	2	Communication (8)
3	Communication (19)	3	Teamwork (7)
4	Social Competence (16)	4	Ethical Behavior and Understanding (6)
5	Teamwork (14)	5	Interdisciplinarity (5)
6	Analytical Thinking (8)		Holistic Thinking (5)
	Ethical Behavior and Understanding (8)		Intercultural Competence (5)
7	(Self-)Learning (7)	6	Responsibility (4)
	Methodological Competence (7)		Leadership (4)
8	Creativity (6)		Presentation Skills (4)
9	Responsibility (5)		Digital Literacy (4)
	Interdisciplinarity (5)	Problem Solving (4)	
	Holistic Thinking (5)	7	(Self-)Learning (3)
	Perseverance (5)		Creativity (3)
10	Impact and Risk Assessment (5)	8	Impact and Risk Assessment (3)
	Leadership (4)		Perseverance (2)
11	Intercultural Competence (4)		Economic Knowledge (2)
	Personal Competence (3)	Willingness to Perform (2)	
	Sustainable Thinking (3)	Management (2)	
	Economic Knowledge (3)	9	Methodological Competence (1)
Digital Literacy (3)	Personal Competence (1)		
12	Willingness to Perform (2)		Sustainable Thinking (1)
	Empathy (2)		Empathy (1)
	Presentation Skills (2)		Recognizing Errors (1)
	Recognizing Errors (2)		
	Management (2)		
13	Openness (1)		

In general, students' perceptions of relevant competencies for engineers go along with other studies [e.g. 6] and frameworks [e.g. 5]. In their systematic review, Passow and Passow [6] provided a broad overview of engineering competencies with regard to their importance, finding that problem solving, communication and teamwork are the three (ABET-mapped) competencies most important for work. At the same time, they concluded that “technical competence [here: technical knowledge and understanding] is inseparably intertwined with effective collaboration” [6, p. 491], which was also highlighted by the students, as, for example, one environmental engineering student stated:

“We engineers will most likely need to continue to work with people to solve problems collaboratively. In terms of that, I think maybe we should work more with each other [in our studies].”

Moreover, social competence itself as well as teamwork and communication were mentioned frequently by the students as relevant competencies. At the same time, those were mentioned most frequently as missing competencies when asked whether students have acquired these competencies in their studies. To illustrate this discrepancy, these competencies are color-coded in Table 1. One environmental engineering student linked these competencies in the context of communicating technical solutions to the public, but also emphasized the relevance of reflecting on the impact of technical developments:

“I would say that social competence should be taken into account even more in education. That you don't just have this extremely specific technical training, but that you also learn a certain way of dealing, especially with people who are not so involved in this technical training. In order to have a better understanding of how solutions affect others, but also how I can present my solution in such a way that others can understand it.”

The competencies that were pointed out as missing most frequently were interpersonal and/or personal competencies. No student mentioned a lack or gap of technical knowledge and understanding, instead they criticized the amount of theory and technical knowledge in comparison to a lack of practical experiences and applications, as one environmental engineering student put it:

“Most of the subjects in my study program are far too theoretical and [...] I think there is a great lack of practical experience in our study program.”

This goes along with a lack of interaction and teamwork, which was pointed out by a student of design and product development:

“I have already had a few bad experiences in the area of my bachelor's study program. On the one hand, there is a lack of any practical reference. A lot of theory is learned, but I missed this practical reference and also teamwork and this whole interaction, which has moved a bit to the back in the study.”

Moreover, students were afraid of not being properly prepared for professional life, as two civil engineering students stated:

“What is particularly difficult is the reference to practice. I don’t really feel prepared considering how many theory subjects you’ve had during your study program and how much theory you retain from it. Although I’m sure these aspects were important, I don’t feel that well prepared for later life. Everything I have learned so far and what I can apply are things that a program will do for me later. That doesn’t make me very happy, but I can understand why people learn it.”

“I don’t have the feeling that I, as a whole, already stand in the market and would be ready to be able to solve more complex solutions independently, on my own responsibility. At the same time, I think that’s also the competence that you have to have as an engineer: understanding complex situations, analyzing them and breaking them down into smaller packages so that you can then work on them and come up with a solution.”

In the last quote, the student voices the feeling of not being able to solve complex problems independently, which students at the same time perceived as one of the most important competencies for engineers.

The lack of practical application and integration of knowledge into practice is a well-known and long discussed problem within engineering education, also regarded as traditional engineering [1, 3, 10, 11]. Thereby students have hardly any opportunity for deep learning experiences which could enable them to solve complex real-world problems [10, 12]. These findings go along with the study by Lermigeaux-Sarrade et al. [9], who asked master’s students about their perceptions of gaining conceptual knowledge and professional skills. The results showed that students ask for more practice and interdisciplinarity in their studies, as well as for more teamwork. In comparison to the study by Miranda et al. [8], the results presented here represent students’ perception of traditional teaching approaches in civil engineering. Students pointed out the exact lack of integrating knowledge, thereby feeling passive in their role as learners.

4 CONCLUSION

This study showed that there are significant gaps with regard to the competencies students perceive to be relevant for professional engineers and the competencies they believe to gain through their education. Especially, this concerns interpersonal and personal competencies, such as teamwork or communication. This becomes particularly relevant concerning the lack of integrating knowledge into practice, showing that this is still not the “center of their education” [1, p. 7]. The study also revealed that students’ perception of relevant competencies is consistent with those discussed in engineering education research. This is novel insofar as qualitative studies from students’ point of view are lacking. The results are particularly relevant as the interview subjects did not receive a predefined list of competencies, but answered freely and articulated competencies on their own. Moreover, the respondents were from different study programs, including both traditional technical

engineering programs such as civil and mechanical engineering and study programs tending multidisciplinary, such as environmental engineering. However, their perceptions were very similar, especially with regard to the lack of practical application and missing interpersonal competencies. As this study is about students' *perception* of their knowledge and competencies, this does not necessarily imply *actual* gained knowledge and competencies. Therefore, an interesting next approach would be to investigate perceptions of both first-year students and graduates to get a deeper understanding of how the perception of both required and acquired competencies changes during the course of their studies. Even though the results represent the subjective perception of the students, the consistency and similarity to other studies is striking in every way. Therefore, on the one hand, the results confirm the emerging call for new and integrated curricula approaches [2], such as the CDIO approach [5, 18]. On the other hand, the results illustrate that despite existing efforts in terms of curriculum development and innovative teaching approaches, both are – in some areas – not yet applied sufficiently.

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